

Synthesis and Characterisation of *N*-Phenyl-*N'*-2(4,6-alkyl/aryl-5-substituted-phenylazopyrimidyl)thiocarbamide as Possible Antibacterials

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The synthesis of varieties of new *N*-phenyl-*N'*-2(4,6-alkyl/aryl-5-substituted-phenylazopyrimidyl)thiocarbamide as possible antibacterials is described. The structure of the compounds is confirmed on the basis of elemental analyses and ir, nmr and mass spectral studies.

PYRIMIDINE nucleus properly substituted at various positions is well known to exhibit biological activities¹⁻³. Hence, the molecular modification of the pyrimidine nucleus has been extensively studied by a large number of workers for developing potential chemotherapeutic agents^{4,5}. As an arylazo grouping is of interest to promote potential antineoplastic and potential antidiabetic activity, a large number of pyrimidines⁶ with arylazo group have also been prepared but their biological activity analysis showed no encouraging results. Since thioureido (-HN-CS-NH-) linkage has been reported to possess significant medicinal importance^{7,8} it was considered interesting to incorporate this moiety in the pyrimidine nucleus with the expectation that this may produce chemotherapeutic agents with reasonable activity. Therefore, a programme of synthesising azopyrimidines having thioureido linkage was developed in this laboratory.

The present communication concerns with the synthesis of *N*-phenyl-*N'*-2(4,6-dimethyl-5-phenylazopyrimidyl)thiocarbamide, *N*-phenyl-*N'*-2(4-methyl-6-phenyl-5-phenylazopyrimidyl)thiocarbamide and *N*-phenyl-*N'*-2(4,6-diphenyl-5-phenylazopyrimidyl)thio-

carbamide. The structures of these compounds have been confirmed on the basis of microanalytical data, ir, nmr and mass spectral studies.

Experimental

The starting materials, 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-arylazo-pyrimidine, 2-amino-4-methyl-6-phenyl-5-arylazopyrimidine and 2-amino-4,6-diphenyl-5-arylazopyrimidine were synthesised in the laboratory by the reported methods^{9,10}. Phenylisothiocyanate was synthesised by the reported procedure¹¹.

2-Amino-4,6-alkyl/aryl-5-arylazopyrimidine (0.01 mol) in benzene (15 ml) was heated on a water-bath for 30 min. When all the pyrimidine dissolved in benzene, phenylisothiocyanate (1.35 g, 0.01 mol) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 10-12 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was washed with petroleum ether (2×10 ml) and recrystallised in dimethylformamide-ethanol (1:1) mixture. The characteristics of various thiocarbamides together with uv and vis maxima are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1- CHARACTERISTICS OF *N*-PHENYL-*N'*-2(4,6-ALKYL/ARYL-5-SUBSTITUTED-PHENYLAZOPYRIMIDYL)THIOCARBAMIDE

Sl. no.	R	R ₁	R ₂	Molecular formula	Colour*	M.p.** °C	Yield %	λ _{max} (nm)	
								uv	vis
1.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ S	B	230	78	240	372
2.	3-OH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₄ S	O	200	74	245	365
3.	4-OH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₄ S	O	235	72	248	370
4.	3-OCH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₄ OS	Y	190	68	245	360
5.	4-OCH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₄ OS	O	170	70	250	358
6.	2-OCH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₄ OS	B	150	70	248	365
7.	4-OCH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₄ OS	B	195	65	240	370

(Table 1 contd.)

8.	2-NO ₂	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	215	67	246	360
9	4-NO ₂	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	200	72	250	355
10.	3-Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ SCl	O	220	71	295	350
11	4-Cl	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ SCl	O	205	74	245	355
12.	2-Br	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ SBr	Y	230	70	240	360
13.	H	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	145	76	245	365
14.	3-CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	205	64	250	362
15.	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	230	70	258	360
16.	3-OCH ₃	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	170	71	265	365
17.	4-OCH ₃	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	160	72	262	350
18.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	O	165	75	240	370
19.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	O	155	72	245	360
20.	2-NO ₂	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	212	68	255	352
21.	4-NO ₂	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	203	62	250	360
22.	3-Cl	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ SCl	O	185	76	255	350
23	4-Cl	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ SCl	O	215	77	265	360
24.	2-Br	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ SBr	O	220	70	260	365
25.	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	215	75	245	370
26.	3 OH ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	Y	194	72	248	366
27.	1-OH ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	Y	210	69	255	358
28	3-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	185	70	250	360
29.	4-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	155	66	245	365
30.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	L	160	67	250	355
31.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	O	186	68	255	360
32.	2-NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	188	65	252	355
33.	4-NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S	B	210	72	260	348
34.	3-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ SCl	Y	205	70	247	365
35.	4-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ SCl	B	195	73	255	345
36.	2-Br	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ SBr	O	205	70	252	348

* B=Brown, O=orange, Y=yellow L=light yellow.

** All determined using Kofler hot apparatus are uncorrected.

The IR and UV spectra of these compounds were recorded using a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer and Specord UV-VIS (C. Zena) spectrophotometer, respectively. The ¹H nmr spectra (TMS as internal standard) were recorded on a Jeol-Fx-100 FT instrument. Mass spectral studies were carried out using Hewlett Packard 5985B instrument.

The structures of these compounds were confirmed on the basis of following consideration: excellent elemental analysis results in the range 0.5-0.8%; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1640-1590 (N=N stretching) and 1510-1490 cm⁻¹ (NH-CS-NH); δ 5.72 (2H, s, NH-CS-NH); mass spectra at 12 eV gave a clear molecular ion peak (M⁺).

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